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Emerging Cislunar Architectures and Spectrum Management Considerations

WWRF51

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Agenda

- NASA Artemis Missions and the Artemis Accords
- Current Cislunar Architecture
- Emerging Cislunar Architecture
- What Could A Cislunar Architecture Look Like?
- How is the Spectrum Regulated?
- Cislunar Spectrum Considerations and Challenges

Artemis Missions

NASA's Artemis campaign, aims to explore the Moon for scientific discovery, technology advancement, and to learn how to live and work on another world as we prepare for human missions to Mars.

- **Artemis I – Unmanned Test Flight**

- Nov 2022 - 25 day mission - Artemis I was the first integrated flight test of NASA's Deep Space Exploration Systems: the Orion spacecraft, Space Launch System (SLS) rocket, with the upgraded Exploration Ground Systems

- **Artemis II - First Artemis Flight With Crew**

- > Late 2025 - Astronauts on their first flight aboard NASA's Space Launch System (SLS) rocket and Orion spacecraft will venture around the Moon. Their mission will be to confirm all of the spacecraft's systems operate as designed with crew aboard in the actual environment of deep space.

- **Artemis III - Humanity's return to the lunar surface**

- Over the course of about 30 days, the Artemis III astronauts will travel to lunar orbit, where two crew members will descend to the surface and spend approximately a week near the South Pole of the Moon conducting new science before returning to lunar orbit to join their crew for the journey back to Earth.

- **Artemis IV – Working on and around the moon**

- Astronauts on Artemis IV will live and work in humanity's first lunar space station

<https://www.nasa.gov/humans-in-space/artemis/>

Artemis Accords

- The Artemis Accords were developed to begin to establish a set of norms for behavior in the cislunar regime and are intended to be a practical flow down for the UN's Outer Space Treaty of 1967
- Artemis Accords launched in October 2020 with 8 participating nations. As of June 2024, over 40 nations have signed the Artemis Accords:
 - Angola, Argentina, Armenia, Australia, Bahrain, Belgium, Brazil, Bulgaria, Canada, Colombia, Czech Republic, Ecuador, France, Germany, Greece, Iceland, India, Israel, Italy, Japan, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Mexico, Netherlands, New Zealand, Nigeria, Peru, Poland, the Republic of Korea, Romania, Rwanda, Saudi Arabia, Singapore, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, the United Arab Emirates, the United Kingdom, the United States, and Uruguay.
- Establishes a common vision for civil space exploration via a set of principles, guidelines, and best practices.
- Adherence to a practical set of principles, guidelines, and best practices in carrying out activities in outer space is intended to increase the safety of operations, reduce uncertainty, and promote the sustainable and beneficial use of space for all humankind.

<https://www.state.gov/artemis-accords/>

Existing Cislunar Architecture

- NASA's Space Communications and Navigation (SCaN) program offers a comprehensive set of standard services based upon its charter to provide communications and navigation services over the full operational life cycle of a mission from launch to de-orbit
- **Deep Space Network (DSN)**
 - Worldwide network of ground stations, operated by NASA JPL, which provides telemetry, commanding, PNT, data, and communications services for interplanetary spacecraft
 - Three DSN ground stations are 120 degrees apart on the globe, meaning all missions beyond GEO are always in view of at least one DSN ground station.
 - The DSN supports a variety of missions and is quickly becoming oversubscribed.
 - 2023 NASA Office of Inspector General (OIG) report which concluded that the DSN is already at capacity, with demand on the network exceeding supply by as much as 40% at times.
- **Near Space Network (NSN)**
 - Worldwide network of ground stations, operated by NASA GSFC, which provides telemetry, commanding, PNT, data, and communications services for interplanetary spacecraft
 - Supports missions in LEO, GEO, HEO, and lunar orbits.
 - In addition to the NSN's terrestrial assets, the Tracking Data and Relay Satellite (TDRS) system in GEO provide additional support to the NSN
 - NSN can provide services up to two million kilometers away from Earth

NSN NEAR SPACE NETWORK **TDRS** **DSN** DEEP SPACE NETWORK

Emerging Cislunar Architectures

- NASA and other governmental agencies would like to move from controlling and maintaining services to procuring services which support future missions
 - Examples:
 - Communications Services Project (CSP) for TDRS replacement
 - NASA Commercial Lunar Payload Services (CLPS) program
 - Industry owned ground stations
- Emerging Cislunar architectures must ensure interoperability to keep mission costs down and prevent 'reinventing the wheel'
- Several competing architectures aim to define what this interoperability will look like, but all have common goal
 - LunaNet
 - Moon to Mars (M2M)
 - NASA Lunar Gateway
 - ESA Moonlight
 - LuCCI – Lunar Command & Control Interoperability
- Consider 3 phases on the path to a Cislunar architecture
 - The 'NOW'
 - The 'Transition'
 - The 'Ubiquitous'

Now

Making Connections for Mission Success in Cislunar

Now

Making Connections for Mission Success in Cislunar

Transition

Making Connections for Mission Success in Cislunar

Making Connections for Mission Success in Cislunar

Ubiquitous

Making Connections for Mission Success in Cislunar

Ubiquitous

Making Connections for Mission Success in Cislunar

Ubiquitous

Making Connections for Mission Success in Cislunar

Spectrum Considerations

- The radio frequency spectrum is a limited natural resource, and should be used efficiently and responsibly
- The desire for high bandwidth communication links to provide high data rates may not always be able to be accommodated as wireless ‘traffic’ increases in the cislunar region
- As the activity in cislunar space and beyond grows, these spectrum accommodations will become increasingly important, as it must be ensured that not only do the Position, Navigation, and Timing (PNT) and communication links not interfere with each other, they must also be compatible with science/radio astronomy frequencies on the lunar surface or cislunar orbit, in addition to Earth-based activities
- For most bands, adjacent to telecommunications and PNT, the band will also be occupied by active and passive sensors, as well as radioastronomy activities. Often times, these active and passive sensors will be always transmitting/receiving, so prior knowledge of frequency, beamwidths, illumination areas, and orbital parameters would be needed to avoid interference
- **Careful planning and coordination will be key to ensure uninterrupted services in the cislunar region**

Spectrum Regulatory Agencies

- **ITU**: International Telecommunication Union
 - The international spectrum management treaty organization...a United Nations organization. 189 nations members. Based in Geneva, Switzerland
- **FCC**: Federal Communications Commission
 - U.S. spectrum management regulatory agency, regulating all ***non-Federal*** Government spectrum. An independent regulatory agency.
- **NTIA**: National Telecommunications & Information Administration
 - Regulating all ***Federal*** Government spectrum. A unit of the Department of Commerce. The Executive Branch telecommunications policy maker, and the President's principal advisor on telecommunications policy.

The law provides FCC and NTIA authority over users...

... Not over spectrum

Table of Frequency Allocations

The shaded part represents the Tropical Zones as defined in Nos.S5.16 to S5.20 and S5.21.

S5-01

NTIA Frequency Allocation Chart (USA/Region 2)

RADIO SERVICES COLOR LEGEND

UNITED STATES FREQUENCY ALLOCATIONS THE RADIO SPECTRUM

U.S. DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE
National Telecommunications and Information Administration
Office of Spectrum Management
October 2013

Spectrum Challenges

- Spectrum allocation needs can lag behind regulatory requirements
 - ITU World Radiocommunications Conference occurs every 3-4 years (last meeting was WRC-23 Dubai in 2023)
 - These meetings result in updates to the international regulations regarding spectrum use, providing both requirements and recommendations
 - Space Frequency Coordination Group (SFCG) was established as a less formal working group for the coordination and resolution of spectrum issues
 - This group includes international space agencies that can come to informal agreements on how space-based spectrum allocations will be effectively used and to attempt to minimize or avoid interference
- Spectrum Allocations for LunaNet have not been fully vetted by the ITU but mostly agreed upon by SFCG
 - All frequencies used on and around the moon that are not DTE must still be allocated for space-to-space

Lunar Electromagnetic Spectrum Architecture

Radio Frequency¹ and Optical⁴

Original Slide courtesy of Cathy Sham: International Committee on Global Navigation Satellite Systems (ICG) – ICG-17 reference: <https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/icg/2023/ICG-17/icg17.02.08.pdf>

Lunar Electromagnetic Spectrum Architecture

Radio Frequency¹ and Optical⁴

Can be used on non interference basis

OK to Use for Proposed Allocation

Use on non interference basis (with potential exceptions)

**Moon is considered a natural object in space
LS-to-LO and LS-to-LS comms are still
considered space-to-space
communications**

Learn more about LunaNet Interoperability Spec.

Original Slide courtesy of Cathy Sham: International Committee on Global Navigation Satellite Systems (ICG) – ICG-17 reference: <https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/icg/2023/ICG-17/icg17.02.08.pdf>

Shielded Zone of the Moon (SZM)

- SZM is a protected region (per ITU Radio Regulations: Article 22) on the backside of the moon reserved for radio astronomy purposes
- ITU recommends frequencies below 2GHz be reserved
 - **Poses issue for Lunar Comms, SAR, and PNT in UHF-, L-, and S-bands**
 - Will require improved out of band filtering for spurious content for operation near this region
 - May prevents full lunar coverage for certain proposed frequencies

Shielded Zone of the Moon

- SFCG proposes in-situ PNT solutions within 2483.5-2500MHz
 - Near Comms bands so comms out-of-band emissions can degrade sensitive receivers
 - Looking into 5010-5030MHz but adjacent to protected radio astronomy band 4990-5000MHz
 - Earth to LO or LS can continue to use GNSS frequencies
 - Can use GNSS frequencies for space-to-space PNT if not interfering with SZM
- SFCG proposes SAR/emergency services at 2299MHz to be used anywhere around the moon
 - This is in addition to the 406-406.1 MHz frequency that can only be used outside of the SZM

Conclusion

- The Artemis campaign aims to return humanity to the Moon's surface (and beyond)
- Existing infrastructure is insufficient for the increased demand that comes with a cislunar communications network
- Emerging architectures aim to promote interoperability such that future missions can reduce costs by taking advantage of an existing cislunar comms and PNT infrastructure
- As the activity in cislunar space and beyond grows, spectrum accommodations will become increasingly important to ensure interference is minimized

Thank You for Listening

QUESTIONS?

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Backup Slides

Spectrum Challenges

- Moon is considered a natural object in space
 - LS-to-LO and LS-to-LS comms are still considered space-to-space communications
- The following frequencies are not allocated for space-to-space use and would be available only on a non-interference basis (NIB)
 - 390-405 MHz
 - 406-406.1 MHz (exception if going DTE)
 - 435-450 MHz
 - 2400-2480 MHz
 - 2483.5-2500 MHz
 - 2503.5-2655 MHz
 - 3500 – 3800 MHz
 - 5150-5835 MHz (with possible exception of 5250-5570 MHz)
 - 5.855 – 5.925 MHz
 - 13.75-14 GHz
 - 14.5-15.35GHz
- The following frequencies are not allocated for Earth-to-space use and would be available only on a non-interference basis (NIB)
 - 22.55 – 23.15 GHz

COOPERATIVE NETWORK

- 1 Poker Flat
- 2 Goldstone
- 3 Madrid
- 4 Weilheim
- 5 Esrange
- 6 Hartebeesthoek
- 7 Malindi
- 8 Kerguelen
- 9 Usuda
- 10 Masuda
- 11 Canberra

CORE ESA NETWORK

- 1 Kourou
- 2 Kiruna
- 3 Redu
- 4 Cebreros (Deep Space)
- 5 New Norcia (Deep Space)
- 6 Santa Maria
- 7 Malargüe (Deep Space)

AUGMENTED NETWORK

- 1 South Point
- 2 Santiago
- 3 Troll
- 4 Svalbard
- 5 Dongara